

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Evolutionary history of quadrupedal walking gaits shows Mammalian release from locomotor constraint.

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S1 Methods

S1.1 Calculation of Duty Factor and Phase

”Hildebrand Plots” are used to visualize footfall patterns by using two quantitative variables to describe quadrupedal locomotion. Traditionally, Hildebrand Plots are first broken up into walking and running based on duty factor (i.e. the percentage of time each foot is on the ground in a steady gait). The second variable of consideration is phase, or the time it takes for a given hindfoot to follow the forefoot on the same side of the body. Limb phases can be divided along an axis into lateral (i.e., a given hindfoot is followed by the ipsilateral forefoot) and diagonal (i.e., a given hindfoot is followed by the contralateral forefoot) sequence gaits. Within each designated sequence, there is another breakdown into a lateral (i.e., fore- and hindfoot on the same side of the body contact ground at roughly the same time) or diagonal (i.e., the diagonally opposing forefoot and hindfoot contact at similar times) couplets [25, 26, 27].

The Hildebrand plot representing phase and duty factor for our data can be found in Main Text Figure 1. We only collected animal gait information if there was a duty factor of above 50%, indicating a walking gait. Footfall data were collected from 244 quadrupedal terrestrial species throughout Gnathostomata. If values were not recorded in the literature (see S2), they were gathered from freely available internet videos. Videos were used if the full gait sequence could be accounted for (duration of time from when a given hindfoot touches the substrate to the next time it contacts), and if footfalls or limb loading could clearly be observed.

Although the equation below uses the right side of the body as an example, it can be used for the left side of the body as well. In practice, we took data from whichever side of the body was clearly visible in the video. A YouTube converter (y2mate.guru) was used to download each video and VirtualDub V.1.9.11 (<http://www.virtualdub.org/>) was used to observe footfall timings frame by frame in order to calculate duty factor and phase. The frame number for each action was taken in order to calculate the equations below. If several gait cycles were observed for a given species, the average phase and duty factor was used. Only walking strides (duty factors > 50) were used for subsequent analyses.

We calculated phase (time for the forefoot to follow the hindfoot on the same side of the body divided by total stride duration) as,

$$\text{Phase} = \frac{\text{RFD} + \text{RHD1}}{\text{RHD2} + \text{RHD1}}, \quad (1)$$

where RHD1 = first time the right hindfoot touches ground, RHD2 = second time the right hindfoot touches ground, and RFD = right forefoot touches ground [27]. We calculated duty factor (time on the ground divided by total stride length) as,

$$\text{Duty Factor} = \frac{\text{RHU} + \text{RHD1}}{\text{RHD2} + \text{RHD1}}. \quad (2)$$

where all abbreviations follow that of equation 1 and RHU = right hindfoot up.

S1.2 Limitations

We recognize several limitations exist within this study regarding our data collection techniques. First is the use of freely available internet videos for data collection. We are not the first group to use this approach [53] and consider this practice to be a resourceful way to gather informative data on gait parameters. Calculating duty factor and phase only requires the timing of footfalls by identifying actions from individual frames, and therefore does not depend on certain video procedures such as specific frame rates or views. While there may

be justified concerns about the physical condition of the animals in the online videos, we only used videos in which the animal appeared healthy and did not deviate from a continuous gait (i.e., not limping, etc.). A supplementary file is provided with the downloaded videos used for data collection if the link provided in the citation (Table S1) is no longer working.

Another important consideration when evaluating our data is speed, which is known to affect several biomechanical gait variables (e.g. [6, 9, 10, 17]). While experimental designs should make every effort to either standardize locomotor speed across trials in initial data collection or account for the confounding influence of speed through appropriate statistical testing, we were unable to account for this in our study. However, in the context of this study we only collected data that included walking gaits (i.e., duty factor > 50%), which assured physiologically similar gaits across subjects [24]. Although our sample is large, and to our knowledge represents one of the most taxonomically diverse samples of tetrapod gaits to date (244 species of Tetrapoda with the inclusion of a few select non-tetrapod Gnathostomes that demonstrate symmetrical quadrupedal walking gaits), we recognize that this sample does not represent all species. Related to this, many species are capable of quite a bit of intraspecific variation (e.g., [31]) that was not accounted for in our initial sampling. These limitations should be considered when interpreting the results of our manuscript, and we hope that future studies will test our conclusions while taking these potentially confounding issues into account.

In this study, we used the total length of the hindlimb as our proxy for limb length. Arguably, a more appropriate proxy would have been effective limb length, which takes into account differences in crouch versus extended limb postures during locomotor behaviors [25]. However, effective limb length is rarely reported in the literature and this would have severely reduced our phylogenetic diversity. Similarly, we used total limb length as a proportion of the cubed root of body mass to reflect relative limb length. While such a ratio is valid, overall body mass includes both the mass of the limbs themselves and the head. A more appropriate measure would have been just to use linear trunk length (i.e., shoulder to hip length) as the denominator. However, as with effective limb length, this measurement is not available for most species. Reconstructing trunk length from isolated vertebrae is marked with its own challenges. Isolating our sample to only species where a trunk length was available would limited the phylogenetic scope of our sample.

S1.3 Phylogenetic ANCOVA

We used phylogenetic regressions to assess the scaling of phase with body mass, limb length, relative limb length, and duty factor (see *Methods*). These last two factors, in particular, have been proposed as important determinants of limb phase; relative limb length as a predictor of LSLC gaits [25, 26, 27] and duty factor as a positive correlate of phase due to mechanical work constraints [53]. Our evolutionary regressions (Main Text Fig. 3) found no support for these hypotheses but it is notable that the long-limbed primates are conspicuous outliers in these plots (Main Text Figs 3C,D) and [53] noted that limb phase in Primates appeared to follow a distinct scaling relationship with duty factor, relative to other tetrapods. Thus, it is possible that the lack of predicted relationships in these analyses results from the influence of these distinctive taxa.

To investigate this possibility, we performed phylogenetically informed Analyses of Covariance (pANCOVA) using the `gls.ancova` function from the `EvoMap` package [49] for R. This method employs a generalized least squares framework to assess whether models with separate intercepts, slopes, or intercepts and slopes for two or more group level effects provide a better fit to the data than a single slope - single intercept model [50]. We compared the fit of models allowing for different combinations of slopes and intercepts for Primates and non-primate mammals for arcsine phase as a function of relative limb length and of arcsine duty factor.

For relative limb length, we recovered non-significant relationships with phase for non-primate mammals (arcsine phase = $0.5524221 + 0.0797901 \times \log(\text{relative limb length})$; $t=0.746929$, $p = 0.4566$) and Primates (arcsine phase = $0.8780632 - 0.0082062 \times \log(\text{relative limb length})$; $t=-0.0379004$, $p = 0.9700$) when analyzed separately (Fig. S4). Unsurprisingly, this result yields no support for differences in slope using pANCOVA (Table S4). The larger intercept found for Primates, compared with non-primate mammals, suggests that

primates may simply occupy a stable but higher phase regime than other mammals, irrespective of relative limb length. Support for a two-intercept model is weak, but not unsubstantial ($F=3.35$, $p = 0.0692$), and better sampling may lend support to this model.

For arcsine duty factor (Fig. S4), we recover non-significant relationships with phase for non-primate mammals ($\arcsin \text{ phase} = 0.6102991 + 0.0320012 \times \arcsin \text{ duty factor}$; $t=0.249758$, $p = 0.8032$) and Primates ($\arcsin \text{ phase} = 1.2493816 - 0.4347258 \times \log(\text{relative limb length})$; $t=-1.557660$, $p = 0.1295$), though the primate scaling relationship is more pronounced than that of non-primates and is clearly more negative. Phylogenetic ANCOVA does not provide support for a distinct slope model alone, but support ($t=3.7$, $p = 0.056$) is recovered for variable intercepts, with Primates again exhibiting a higher ancestral phase, relative to duty factor, compared with non-primate mammals. Some degree of support for distinct slopes and intercepts is also present (Table S4). Taken as a whole, these results provide no further support for Hildebrand's hypothesis that relative limb length drives the use of LSLC gaits or Usherwood and Self-Davies' hypothesis that mechanical work demands constrain the relationship between duty factor and phase to be positive[53]. They do corroborate the idea that Primates are distinctive, relative to other mammals, in their use of symmetric walking gaits.

S2 Supplementary Figures

Figure S1: 95% credible set of rate shifts from BAMM analysis of phase. For each panel, f is the frequency of that shift configuration in the posterior sample. A shift in mammals (yellow clade) is recovered in all most credible configurations. A single additional shift within Lepidosauria is recovered in about 70% of the credible set but the precise location of this shift cannot be determined.

Figure S2: The configuration with the highest posterior probability recovers a single shift in the branch leading to mammals (red branches).

Figure S3: Mean rates of phase evolution, averaged over all possible shift configurations. Branch labels indicate marginal probabilities of a shift occurring along that edge. The large label corresponds to the mammalian shift. Smaller labels correspond to uncertain shift positions in acrodont squamates, which result in the fastest model-averaged rates of all.

Figure S4: ANCOVAs for non-primates (blue) and Primates (orange)

S3 Supplementary Tables

Table S1: Table with species information and references for duty factor and phase. The reported numbers for each gait parameter are the averaged value if several strides were taken. Habitat categories were determined using gait sources and Animal Diversity Web (<https://animaldiversity.org/>). Q = aquatic, A = arboreal, T = terrestrial. FMNH = Field Museum of Natural History, Chicago IL; NMNH = Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, Washington D.C.; UWBM = University of Washington Burke Museum, Seattle WA. Data on stride number was not reported in [38].

Class	Order	Species	Strides	Duty		Ref	Habitat
				Factor	Phase		
Actinopterygii	Cypriniformes	<i>Cryptotora thamicola</i>	6	65.45	51.18	[11]	Q
Actinopterygii	Lophiiformes	<i>Antennarius striatus</i>	5	67.65	46.04	[71]	Q
Lissamphibia	Anura	<i>Kassina maculata</i>	1	78	44	[53]	T
Lissamphibia	Anura	<i>Agalychnis callidryas</i>	3	82.27	34.26	[64]	A
Lissamphibia	Anura	<i>Breviceps mossambicus</i>	5	67.87	39.09	[136]	T
Lissamphibia	Anura	<i>Lepidobatrachus laevis</i>	4	65.02	39.04	[128]	Q
Lissamphibia	Anura	<i>Pelobates syriacus</i>	4	79.99	32.39	[166]	T
Lissamphibia	Anura	<i>Phyllomedusa hypochondrialis</i>	6	70.03	39.18	[110]	A
Lissamphibia	Anura	<i>Rana catesbeiana</i>	4	71.77	39.79	[73]	T
Lissamphibia	Anura	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	7	75.10	39.05	[155]	T
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Ambystoma tigrinum</i>	1	80	40	[53]	T
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Andrias japonicus</i>	1	74	40	[53]	Q
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Ambystoma maculatum</i>	8	72.14	44.34	[83]	T
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Ambystoma mexicanum</i>	2	53.82	44.86	[58]	Q
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Ambystoma texanum</i>	10	67.68	44.50	[175]	T
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Cryptobranchus alleganiensis</i>	4	59.39	50.30	[120]	Q
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Dicamptodon tenebrosus</i>	5	72.08	36.42	[68]	T
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Hynobius kimurae</i>	2	71.09	49.49	[147]	T
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Necturus maculosus</i>	3	71.88	41.67	[105]	Q
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Plethodon vehiculum</i>	6	71.46	45.36	[150]	T
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Pseudotriton ruber</i>	5	75.77	49.59	[77]	Q
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Rhyacotriton variegatus</i>	4	77.13	43.83	[48]	Q
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Salamandra infraimmaculata</i>	4	76.46	36.91	[69]	T
Lissamphibia	Urodela	<i>Taricha torosa</i>	7	65.59	38.16	[96]	T
Archelosauria	Crocodylia	<i>Alligator mississippiensis</i>	3	87	42	[53]	T
Archelosauria	Crocodylia	<i>Caiman crocodilus</i>	2	78	43	[53]	T
Archelosauria	Crocodylia	<i>Crocodylus palustris</i>	1	78	49	[53]	T

Class	Order	Species	Strides	Duty		Ref	Habitat
				Factor	Phase		
Archelosauria	Crocodylia	Gavialis gangeticus	1	52.24	41.79	[164]	T
Archelosauria	Opisthocomiformes	Opisthocomus hoazin	4	92.96	39.06	[1]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Centrochelys sulcata	2	82	42	[53]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Apalone spinifera	2	70.71	39.05	[70]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Carettochelys insculpta	2	58.41	50.47	[93]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Chelonoidis nigra	1	84.88	51.16	[82]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Chelus fimbriata	2	59.46	45.95	[103]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Chelydra serpentina	2	62.91	55.49	[61]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Chersina angulata	4	67.22	39.93	[94]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Chrysemys picta	3	73.43	29.35	[90]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Cuora amboinensis	2	74.57	41.57	[152]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Deirochelys reticularia	3	73.58	43.29	[86, 159]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Podocnemis expansa	2	73.05	45.21	[92]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Sternotherus carinatus	2	72.16	46.57	[157]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Terrapene carolina	2	59.63	43.38	[135, 118]	T
Archelosauria	Testudines	Testudo horsfieldii	41	83.88	38.64	[17]	T
Chondrichthyes	Orectolobiformes	Hemiscyllium ocellatum	6	71.49	47.37	[43]	Q
Dipnoi	Lepidosireniformes	Protopterus annectens	3	66.76	43.84	[36]	Q
Lepidosauria	Sphenodontia	Sphenodon punctatus	22	57.18	43.54	[44]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Acanthodactylus boskianus	-	53	57	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Ameiva ameiva	-	53	38	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Eulamprus quoyii	26	56.67	57.07	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Eumeces schneideri	-	73	50	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Leiocephalus schreibersi	34	56.36	51.30	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Lepidophyma flavimaculatum	2	50.53	55.45	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Oplurus cuvieri	20	52.04	52.18	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Sceloporus malachiticus	20	52.93	52.13	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Smaug warreni	2	53.45	50.34	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Tracheloptychus petersi	-	72	43	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Tropidurus torquatus	1	50.12	44.24	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Tupinambis teguixin	-	64	46	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Varanus exanthematicus	-	69	40	[38]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Amblyrhynchus cristatus	1	85	41	[53]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Conolophus pallidus	1	84	47	[53]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Eublepharis macularius	2	79	43	[53]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Iguana iguana	2	75	44	[53]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Pogona vitticeps	1	78	48	[53]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Varanus komodoensis	3	77	45	[53]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Varanus salvator	1	81	40	[53]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Anolis carolinensis	4	77.74	40.03	[156]	A
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Anolis equestris	2	60.19	43.70	[87]	A
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Anolis proboscis	2	64.31	36.67	[154]	A
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Aspidoscelis inornata	3	58.89	52.22	[146]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Basiliscus plumifrons	1	50	33.33	[75]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Chamaeleo calypttratus	8	65.55	44.07	[137, 121]	A
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Chamaeleo namaquensis	6	75.03	40.94	[56]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Chamaeleo zeylanicus	6	65.35	59.22	[123, 78]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Ecleopopus gaudichaudii	1	66.67	33.33	[100]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Furcifer labordi	3	68.34	44.87	[81]	A
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Furcifer pardalis	8	70.09	35.15	[165]	A
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Gekko gekko	2	57.98	28.99	[88]	A
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Heloderma suspectum	6	71.11	46.69	[137]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Lanthanotus borneensis	3	60.22	48.04	[140]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Matobosaurus validus	2	69.83	52.72	[47]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Moloch horridus	4	90.03	36.07	[133]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Phrynosoma platyrhinos	1	91.67	58.33	[172]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Podarcis siculus	7	61.15	43.41	[153]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Shinisaurus crocodilurus	1	76.19	57.14	[107]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Tiliqua scincoides	6	68.69	46.92	[132]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Timon lepidus	3	69.72	42.5	[143]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Trioceros jacksonii	4	61.35	42.08	[144]	A
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Xenosaurus platyceps	1	85	60	[108]	T
Lepidosauria	Squamata	Stellagama stellio	3	51.49	50.11	[38]	T
Mammalia	Afrotheria	Dendrohyrax arboreus	1	55.55	22.22	[158]	A
Mammalia	Afrotheria	Orycteropus afer	3	69.98	49.46	M.C.G. ¹	T
Mammalia	Afrotheria	Elephas maximus	1	73	19	[53]	T
Mammalia	Afrotheria	Loxodonta africana	4	74	17	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Cephalophus natalensis	2	60	22.5	[60]	T

¹Unpublished data

Class	Order	Species	Strides	Duty		Ref	Habitat
				Factor	Phase		
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Okapia johnstoni	4	60.65	16.91	[130, 63]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Vicugna pacos	41	55.81	12.93	[41]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Hippopotamus amphibius	4	76	45	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Oryx gazella	2	66.66	14.81	[169]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Pecari tajacu	2	65.17	23.79	[127]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Lama glama	1	72	17	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Cephalophus silvicultor	2	67.2	23.12	[89]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Tragelaphus strepsiceros	3	62.68	32.03	[80]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Giraffa camelopardalis	5	68	14	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Camelus dromedarius	2	75.02	22.79	[41]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Ammotragus lervia	1	71	26	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Camelus bactrianus	1	72	21	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Sus scrofa	2	70.80	25.75	[104]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Moschiola meminna	2	68.18	20.76	[84]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Aepyceros melampus	1	68	19	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Bison bison	1	71	16	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Bos taurus	5	69	29	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Capra aegagrus	1	72	23	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Connochaetes taurinus	11	72	18	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Odocoileus virginianus	2	69	31	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Ovis aries	1	68	28	[53]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Alcelaphus buselaphus	2	72.41	18.97	[171]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Antilocapra americana	2	62.02	17.95	[101]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Bubalus bubalis	2	63.17	16.96	[59]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Kobus ellipsiprymnus	2	67.16	20.9	[79]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Moschus leucogaster	2	72.02	30.21	[119]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Muntiacus muntjak	2	67.64	23.42	[67]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Nanger granti	3	67.38	21.05	[74]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Oreotragus oreotragus	2	64.29	42.86	[66]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Ovis canadensis	3	59.44	21.69	[139]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Saiga tatarica	2	66.59	21.36	[85]	T
Mammalia	Artiodactyla	Cervus elaphus	3	63.47	28.19	[141]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Crocuta crocuta	1	66	10	[53]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Ursus americanus	1	67	18	[53]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Ursus arctos	1	65	17	[53]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Ursus maritimus	1	68	16	[53]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Nasua nasua	30	70.51	22.54	[17]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Cuon alpinus	2	69.62	17.95	[116]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Paradoxurus hermaphroditus	3	74.46	24.12	[138]	A
Mammalia	Carnivora	Nandinia binotata	2	58.93	21.43	[91]	A
Mammalia	Carnivora	Zalophus wolfebaeki	2	59.48	19.11	[111]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Acinonyx jubatus	1	70	18	[53]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Lynx rufus	1	71	17	[53]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Mungos mungo	2	60	16	[53]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Panthera leo	3	68	15	[53]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Canis aureus	3	73.29	24.26	[112]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Canis lupus	1	60.34	18.97	[72]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Caracal caracal	23	65.76	20.07	[17]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Chrysocyon brachyurus	3	62.85	13.18	[57]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Felis catus	37	63.88	21.74	[17]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Leopardus pardalis	7	60.88	19.12	[65]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Leptailurus serval	31	58.31	23.49	[17]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Mellivora capensis	2	62.05	26.14	[55]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Panthera onca	1	64.1	10.26	[99]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Panthera tigris	20	64.41	20.32	[17]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Vulpes vulpes	2	63.70	32.52	[134]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Procyon lotor	1	71	14	[53]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Mephitis mephitis	2	74.17	25.63	[97]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Ailuropoda melanoleuca	2	66.04	20.17	[174]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Ailurus fulgens	2	61.17	20.42	[162]	A
Mammalia	Carnivora	Arctictis binturong	3	70.64	21.41	[148]	A
Mammalia	Carnivora	Cryptoprocta ferox	2	70.43	27.48	[131]	A
Mammalia	Carnivora	Enhydra lutris	2	67.16	27.29	[125, 76]	T
Mammalia	Carnivora	Potos flavus	30	51.16	58.33	[17]	A
Mammalia	Chiroptera	Mystacina tuberculata	7	60.78	40.68	[45]	A
Mammalia	Chiroptera	Desmodus rotundus	47	68.15	29.51	[14]	A
Mammalia	Chiroptera	Pteropus vampyrus	43	73.19	29.84	[14]	A
Mammalia	Cingulata	Priodontes maximus	3	59.12	64.79	[124]	T
Mammalia	Cingulata	Dasybus novemcinctus	2	54.54	36.36	[62]	T
Mammalia	Dasyuromorphia	Myrmecobius fasciatus	2	55	30	[95]	T

Class	Order	Species	Strides	Duty			Ref	Habitat
				Factor	Phase			
Mammalia	Dasyuromorphia	Sarcophilus harrisi	4	62.32	20.12	[151, 168]	T	
Mammalia	Dasyuromorphia	Dasyurus maculatus	16	64.27	41.40	[5, 160]	T	
Mammalia	Didelphimorphia	Philander opossum	18	62.84	54.058	[5]	T	
Mammalia	Didelphimorphia	Caluromys philander	85	67.03	58	[37]	A	
Mammalia	Didelphimorphia	Monodelphis domestica	15	68.60	46.31	[37]	T	
Mammalia	Didelphimorphia	Didelphis virginiana	2	76.54	34.86	[129]	T	
Mammalia	Diprotodontia	Petaurus breviceps	160	61.5	45	[46]	A	
Mammalia	Diprotodontia	Pseudocheirus peregrinus	13	58.14	53.17	[5]	A	
Mammalia	Diprotodontia	Phascolarctos cinereus	4	69.70	45.51	[98, 126]	A	
Mammalia	Diprotodontia	Vombatus ursinus	2	67.33	22.42	[167]	T	
Mammalia	Diprotodontia	Dendrolagus goodfellowi	2	68	22	[170]	A	
Mammalia	Diprotodontia	Trichosurus vulpecula	19	56.56	66.97	[5]	A	
Mammalia	Diprotodontia	Acrobates pygmaeus	22	55.35	50.19	[34]	A	
Mammalia	Diprotodontia	Lasiorhinus krefftii	1	73	18	[53]	T	
Mammalia	Eulipotyphla	Talpa europaea	1	63.66	33.33	[113]	T	
Mammalia	Eulipotyphla	Erinaceus europaeus	1	62.96	33.33	[115]	T	
Mammalia	Monotremata	Zaglossus bruijnii	3	67.16	24.28	[13, 149]	T	
Mammalia	Monotremata	Ornithorhynchus anatinus	10	58.60	44.36	[54]	T	
Mammalia	Monotremata	Tachyglossus aculeatus	1	67	13	[53]	T	
Mammalia	Peramelemorphia	Isodon macrourus	11	74.39	41.79	[3]	T	
Mammalia	Perissodactyla	Equus asinus	1	73	25	[53]	T	
Mammalia	Perissodactyla	Ceratotherium simum	2	68	21	[53]	T	
Mammalia	Perissodactyla	Tapirus bairdii	2	65.01	21.97	[145]	T	
Mammalia	Perissodactyla	Tapirus terrestris	1	70	26	[53]	T	
Mammalia	Perissodactyla	Tapirus indicus	1	61	26	[53]	T	
Mammalia	Perissodactyla	Equus burchellii	28	67	24	[53]	T	
Mammalia	Perissodactyla	Equus caballus	2	67	24	[53]	T	
Mammalia	Pilosa	Myrmecophaga tridactyla	1	70	27	[53]	T	
Mammalia	Pilosa	Cyclopes didactylus	2	87.63	64.59	[163]	A	
Mammalia	Pilosa	Bradypus variegatus	1	78.57	52.04	[109]	A	
Mammalia	Pilosa	Choloepus didactylus	37	72.63	49.43	[15]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Ateles paniscus	46	60.60	63.99	[18]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Nycticebus pygmaeus	22	53.52	55.67	[19]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Mandrillus sphinx	2	64.00	56.09	[102]	T	
Mammalia	Primates	Ateles geoffroyi	24	60.68	71.88	[17]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Lemur catta	89	64.50	65.25	[20]	T	
Mammalia	Primates	Aotus nancymaeae	34	59.59	58.38	[19]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Leontopithecus rosalia	2	65.77	58.27	M.C.G. ²	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Papio ursinus	2	64.76	56.90	[117]	T	
Mammalia	Primates	Loris tardigradus	33	51.89	55.85	[19]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Gorilla gorilla	2	61.55	43.43	[122]	T	
Mammalia	Primates	Pan troglodytes	2	62.78	48.06	[161]	T	
Mammalia	Primates	Pygathrix nemaeus	7	63.21	64.94	[16]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Cebus capucinus	39	59.38	62.84	[17]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Rhinopithecus roxellana	193	69.44	62.15	M.C.G. ³	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Macaca fascicularis	60	60.21	63.08	[19]	T	
Mammalia	Primates	Ateles fusciceps	22	59.80	71.24	[17]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Alouatta seniculus	27	68.33	56.90	[18]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Saimiri sciureus	98	54.26	58.77	[19]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Pithecia pithecia	28	65.78	28.92	[18]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Chiropotes satanas	31	66.84	44.79	[18]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Sapajus apella	29	65.60	49.54	[18]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Macaca mulatta	22	62.76	63.03	[17]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Trachypithecus hatinhensis	12	60.93	61.45	[16]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Cheirogaleus medius	32	54.58	55.44	[19]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Daubentonia madagascariensis	50	57.36	65.79	[19]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Hapalemur griseus	20	61.92	64.62	[17]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Pygathrix cinerea	15	66.19	64.50	[16]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Varecia variegata	57	57.20	64.54	[20]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Eulemur mongoz	29	53.53	62.44	[16]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Propithecus coquereli	49	63.27	62.89	[20]	T	
Mammalia	Primates	Trachypithecus delacouri	6	60.89	59.73	[16]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Trachypithecus phayrei	11	63.83	61.25	[16]	A	
Mammalia	Primates	Trachypithecus poliocephalus	10	60.99	64.10	[16]	A	
Mammalia	Rodentia	Apodemus agrarius	93	74.01	35.52	[30]	T	
Mammalia	Rodentia	Apodemus flavicollis	79	72.51	28.77	[30]	T	
Mammalia	Rodentia	Mesocricetus auratus	1	70	45	[53]	T	

²Unpublished data

³Unpublished data

Class	Order	Species	Strides	Duty		Ref	Habitat
				Factor	Phase		
Mammalia	Rodentia	Micromys minutus	66	65.63	34.05	[31]	T
Mammalia	Rodentia	Castor canadensis	3	74.16	36.68	[142]	T
Mammalia	Rodentia	Mus musculus	1	86	40	[53]	T
Mammalia	Rodentia	Sciurus niger	7	67.06	26.26	M.C.G. ⁴	A
Mammalia	Rodentia	Hydrochoerus hydrochaeris	2	69.21	28.16	[106]	T
Mammalia	Rodentia	Thallomys paedulcus	14	71.88	31.89	[32]	T
Mammalia	Rodentia	Rattus norvegicus	1	62	36	[53]	T
Mammalia	Rodentia	Muscardinus avellanarius	10	64.25	36.74	[33]	T
Mammalia	Rodentia	Myodes glareolus	54	68.35	25.86	[30]	T
Mammalia	Rodentia	Sciurus griseus	6	66.29	35.33	[114]	A
Mammalia	Rodentia	Erethizon dorsatum	2	75	29	[53]	T
Mammalia	Scandentia	Tupaia tana	2	64.62	38.08	[173]	A

⁴Unpublished data

Table S2: Body mass (g) and absolute hindlimb length (mm) (sum of femur, tibia, and metatarsal III) data for mammalian species.

Order	Species	Body Mass	Ref	Limb Length	Ref
Afrotheria	Dendrohyrax arboreus	2981.11	[29]	147.37	FMNH 163768
Afrotheria	Elephas maximus	3269794.34	[29]	1902.45	FMNH 49894
Afrotheria	Loxodonta africana	3824539.93	[29]	1860	[28]
Afrotheria	Orycteropus afer	56175.2	[29]	399.58	FMNH 33477
Artiodactyla	Aepyceros melampus	52591.69	[29]	723	[39]
Artiodactyla	Alcelaphus buselaphus	160937.86	[29]	805	[39]
Artiodactyla	Ammotragus lervia	94202.22	[29]	628.97	FMNH 52423
Artiodactyla	Antilocapra americana	47450.01	[29]	733	[39]
Artiodactyla	Bison bison	624577.07	[29]	992	[39]
Artiodactyla	Bos taurus	618642.42	[29]	958	[39]
Artiodactyla	Bubalus bubalis	929500.97	[29]	815	[39]
Artiodactyla	Camelus bactrianus	554515.91	[29]	1291	FMNH 60013
Artiodactyla	Camelus dromedarius	492714.47	[29]	1418	FMNH 52325
Artiodactyla	Capra aegagrus	47386.47	[29] ⁵	546	[39]
Artiodactyla	Cephalophus natalensis	12724.51	[29]	328.93	FMNH 101847 ⁶
Artiodactyla	Cephalophus silvicultor	62006.6	[29]	615	FMNH 174410
Artiodactyla	Cervus elaphus	166562.5	[29]	859.0135	[8]
Artiodactyla	Connochaetes taurinus	198619.68	[29]	920	[39]
Artiodactyla	Giraffa camelopardalis	964654.73	[29]	1448.5	FMNH 34424
Artiodactyla	Hippopotamus amphibius	1536310.4	[29]	857.47	FMNH 12780
Artiodactyla	Kobus ellipsiprymnus	204393.48	[29]	946	[39]
Artiodactyla	Lama glama	78322.67	[29]	790	FMNH 15569
Artiodactyla	Moschiola meminna	3130.95	[29]	193.35	FMNH 98272
Artiodactyla	Moschus leucogaster	17000	[7]	465	[39]
Artiodactyla	Muntiacus muntjak	17611.59	[29]	368	[39]
Artiodactyla	Nanger granti	55464.46	[29]	788	[39]
Artiodactyla	Odocoileus virginianus	75901.25	[29]	560	[39]
Artiodactyla	Okapia johnstoni	230001.14	[29]	900	FMNH 104923
Artiodactyla	Oreotragus oreotragus	13486.55	[29]	409	[39]
Artiodactyla	Oryx gazella	188404.45	[29]	823	FMNH 127968
Artiodactyla	Ovis aries	39097.89	[29]	537	[39]
Artiodactyla	Ovis canadensis	74644.87	[29]	739	[39]
Artiodactyla	Pecari tajacu	21133.69	[29]	350.54	FMNH 134434
Artiodactyla	Saiga tatarica	37734.01	[29]	577	[39]
Artiodactyla	Sus scrofa	84471.54	[29]	534.89	FMNH 97884
Artiodactyla	Tragelaphus strepsiceros	206056.41	[29]	981	FMNH 18815
Artiodactyla	Vicugna pacos	44400	[40]	685	FMNH 121665
Carnivora	Acinonyx jubatus	49270	[22]	616.87	[22]
Carnivora	Ailuropoda melanoleuca	117999.99	[29]	552.3	[42], [4]
Carnivora	Ailurus fulgens	5170.08	[29]	236.4	[42], [4]
Carnivora	Panthera leo	175890	[22]	741.72	[22]
Carnivora	Panthera onca	82550	[22]	549.75	[22]
Carnivora	Panthera tigris	142000	[22]	744.94	[22]
Carnivora	Paradoxurus hermaphroditus	3200	[29]	227.38	FMNH 140476
Carnivora	Potos flavus	2441.81	[29]	234.89	[17]
Carnivora	Procyon lotor	6179	[35]	320	[35]
Carnivora	Ursus americanus	110500	[29]	639.7348	[8]
Carnivora	Ursus arctos	196287.5	[29]	709.5778	[8]
Carnivora	Ursus maritimus	371703.81	[29]	785.2356	[8]
Carnivora	Vulpes vulpes	4750	[22]	318.38	[22]
Carnivora	Zalophus wollebaeki	158000	[52]	415	FMNH 226759
Chiroptera	Desmodus rotundus	23.1	[45]	47.471	[45]
Chiroptera	Mystacina tuberculata	13.9	[45]	41.573	[45]
Chiroptera	Pteropus vampyrus	1027.54	[29]	199.05	[14]
Cingulata	Dasyopus novemcinctus	3580	[51]	163.78	[51]
Cingulata	Priodontes maximus	40641.89	[29]	346.5	FMNH 72913
Dasyuromorphia	Dasyurus maculatus	3284.15	[29]	181.877	FMNH 57803
Dasyuromorphia	Myrmecobius fasciatus	511.44	[29]	112.04	FMNH 19982
Dasyuromorphia	Sarcophilus harrisii	8202.25	[29]	214.237	FMNH 46006
Didelphimorphia	Caluromys philander	246.47	[29]	105.05	[2]
Didelphimorphia	Didelphis virginiana	2290	[51]	154.79	[51]
Didelphimorphia	Monodelphis domestica	70	[51]	56.19	[51]
Didelphimorphia	Philander opossum	425.81	[29]	125.05	[2]
Diprotodontia	Acrobates pygmaeus	13.84	[29]	36.888	UWBM 68896

⁵Used *Capra hircus*

⁶Used *Cephalophus monticola*

Order	Species	Body		Limb	
		Mass	Ref	Length	Ref
Diprotodontia	<i>Dendrolagus goodfellowi</i>	7948.78	[29]	308.61	FMNH 98158
Diprotodontia	<i>Lasiorhinus krefftii</i>	31849.99	[29]	275.66	FMNH 49085 ⁷
Diprotodontia	<i>Petaurus breviceps</i>	120.76	[29]	77.818	FMNH 129430
Diprotodontia	<i>Phascolarctos cinereus</i>	6528.74	[29]	267.58	FMNH 19803
Diprotodontia	<i>Pseudocheirus peregrinus</i>	895.22	[29]	133.4	FMNH 134502
Diprotodontia	<i>Trichosurus vulpecula</i>	2800	[51]	213.82	[51]
Diprotodontia	<i>Vombatus ursinus</i>	26000	[29]	275.66	FMNH 49085
Eulipotyphla	<i>Erinaceus europaeus</i>	777.95	[29]	101.65	[51]
Eulipotyphla	<i>Talpa europaea</i>	87.53	[29]	46.28	⁸
Monotremata	<i>Ornithorhynchus anatinus</i>	1484.25	[29]	157.79	⁹
Monotremata	<i>Tachyglossus aculeatus</i>	3700	[51]	127.74	[51]
Monotremata	<i>Zaglossus bruijnii</i>	8951.71	[29]	212.558	[12]
Peramelemorphia	<i>Isoodon macrourus</i>	1505.77	[29]	192.98	NMNH 238438
Perissodactyla	<i>Ceratotherium simum</i>	2285939.43	[29]	1057	FMNH 125413
Perissodactyla	<i>Equus asinus</i>	164998.49	[29]	748.1695	[8]
Perissodactyla	<i>Equus burchellii</i>	279160.65	[29]	881	[39]
Perissodactyla	<i>Equus caballus</i>	403598.53	[29]	1063	[39]
Perissodactyla	<i>Tapirus bairdii</i>	293781.59	[29]	665.65	FMNH 34665
Perissodactyla	<i>Tapirus indicus</i>	311209.19	[29]	662	FMNH 60010
Perissodactyla	<i>Tapirus terrestris</i>	169496.64	[29]	638.54	FMNH 53730
Pilosa	<i>Bradypus variegatus</i>	4136.36	[29]	217.35	FMNH 69589
Pilosa	<i>Choloepus didactylus</i>	6646.5	[29]	356.99	FMNH 95448
Pilosa	<i>Cyclopes didactylus</i>	263.95	[29]	91.86	FMNH 61853
Pilosa	<i>Myrmecophaga tridactyla</i>	29531.83	[29]	486.29	FMNH 28309
Primates	<i>Alouatta seniculus</i>	6398.31	[29]	359.22	FMNH 93248
Primates	<i>Aotus nancymaae</i>	791.03	[29]	215.28	FMNH 127397
Primates	<i>Ateles fusciceps</i>	9067.94	[29]	384.64	FMNH 68810
Primates	<i>Ateles geoffroyi</i>	7582.4	[29]	432.53	FMNH 121526
Primates	<i>Ateles paniscus</i>	8697.25	[29]	432.53	FMNH 121546 ¹⁰
Primates	<i>Cebus capucinus</i>	3005.99	[29]	291.03	FMNH 22396
Primates	<i>Cheirogaleus medius</i>	196.76	[29]	89.27	This study
Primates	<i>Chiropotes satanas</i>	2967.27	[29]	291.38	FMNH 95519
Primates	<i>Daubentonia madagascariensis</i>	2731.37	[29]	362.12	This study
Primates	<i>Eulemur mongoz</i>	1771.13	[29]	313.78	[17]
Primates	<i>Gorilla gorilla</i>	112588.99	[29]	713.32	FMNH 18402
Primates	<i>Hapalemur griseus</i>	916	[29]	214.86	[17]
Primates	<i>Lemur catta</i>	2626.48	[29]	294.15	FMNH 127368
Primates	<i>Leontopithecus rosalia</i>	592.52	[29]	172.08	FMNH 134505
Primates	<i>Loris tardigradus</i>	249.22	[29]	132.74	FMNH 180671
Primates	<i>Macaca fascicularis</i>	4569.32	[29]	313.28	FMNH 61026
Primates	<i>Macaca mulatta</i>	6455.19	[29]	311.22	FMNH 99668
Primates	<i>Mandrillus sphinx</i>	16685.06	[29]	564.59	FMNH 121292
Primates	<i>Nycticebus pygmaeus</i>	342.32	[29]	144.04	FMNH 108856
Primates	<i>Pan troglodytes</i>	45000	[29]	613.14	FMNH 18410
Primates	<i>Papio ursinus</i>	17729.44	[29]	407.61	FMNH 159985
Primates	<i>Pithecia pithecia</i>	1667.19	[29]	285.07	FMNH 95509
Primates	<i>Propithecus coquereli</i>	4189.27	[29]	482.8	[17]
Primates	<i>Pygathrix cinerea</i>	10900	[16]	476.73	[16]
Primates	<i>Pygathrix nemaeus</i>	9411.1	[29]	441.83	FMNH 214917
Primates	<i>Rhinopithecus roxellana</i>	13456.8	[29]	399.82	FMNH 31143
Primates	<i>Saimiri sciureus</i>	749.47	[29]	199.81	FMNH 93519
Primates	<i>Sapajus apella</i>	2758.38	[29]	290.62	FMNH 98046
Primates	<i>Trachypithecus delacouri</i>	8200	[21]	452.21	[16]
Primates	<i>Trachypithecus hatinhensis</i>	8700	[16]	487.94	[16]
Primates	<i>Trachypithecus phayrei</i>	7681.72	[29]	496.73	[16]
Primates	<i>Trachypithecus poliocephalus</i>	9000	[16]	466.64	[16]
Primates	<i>Varecia variegata</i>	3849.99	[29]	323.41	[17]
Rodentia	<i>Apodemus agrarius</i>	21.11	[29]	59.96	FMNH 179117 ¹¹
Rodentia	<i>Apodemus flavicollis</i>	31.6	[29]	59.96	FMNH 179117 ¹²
Rodentia	<i>Castor canadensis</i>	18124.41	[29]	201.94	FMNH 134455
Rodentia	<i>Erethizon dorsatum</i>	7419.46	[29]	206	M.C.G. ¹³
Rodentia	<i>Hydrochoerus hydrochaeris</i>	48144.91	[29]	473.96	FMNH 51636

⁷Used *Vombatus ursinus*

⁸Zhe-Xi Luo personal collection

⁹Zhe-Xi Luo personal collection

¹⁰Used *Ateles geoffroyi*

¹¹Used *Apodemus mystacinus*

¹²Used *Apodemus mystacinus*

¹³Unpublished data

Order	Species	Body Mass	Ref	Limb Length	Ref
Rodentia	<i>Mesocricetus auratus</i>	98.6	[29]	65.02	FMNH 122237
Rodentia	<i>Micromys minutus</i>	6.99	[29]	28.41	FMNH 129466
Rodentia	<i>Mus musculus</i>	19.3	[29]	31.2	FMNH 140454
Rodentia	<i>Muscardinus avellanarius</i>	29.19	[29]	41.44	FMNH 157986 ¹⁴
Rodentia	<i>Myodes glareolus</i>	20.73	[29]	38.86	FMNH 163360 ¹⁵
Rodentia	<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	282.89	[29]	94.63	[39]
Rodentia	<i>Sciurus griseus</i>	703.85	[29]	143.94	FMNH 178182 ¹⁶
Rodentia	<i>Sciurus niger</i>	765.9	[23]	179.8	FMNH 186950
Rodentia	<i>Thallomys paedulus</i>	77.7	[29]	49.64	FMNH 211205 ¹⁷
Scandentia	<i>Tupaia tana</i>	182.33	[29]	108.85	FMNH 145465

¹⁴Used *Muscardinus graphiurus*

¹⁵Used *Myodes gapperi*

¹⁶Used *Sciurus carolinensis*

¹⁷Used *Grammomys macmillani*

Table S3: Estimated ancestral phase values for key nodes derived using a phylogeny with temporal branch lengths and rate-based branch lengths

Clade	time-based	rate-based
	mean (95% CIs)	mean (95% CIs)
Gnathostomes	44.44 (17.72–73.04)	46.76 (41.24–52.32)
Tetrapods	42.54 (24.19–62.03)	42.44 (37.14–47.83)
Amniotes	42.28 (25.21–60.36)	42.36 (36.32–48.52)
Mammals	37.99 (22.08–55.36)	40.68 (30.28–51.52)
Theria	37.90 (23.45–53.54)	41.46 (28.87–54.65)

Table S4: Comparison of fits for variable slope, variable intercept, and variable slope plus intercept models to single slope intercept models for phase as a function of relative limb length and of duty factor.

predictor	model	df	SS	F	P
relative limb length	Common model	2	9.6684		
	Variable Slopes	3	9.5055	2.5876	0.1098
	Variable Intercept	3	9.4586	3.3497	0.0692
	Variable Slope + Intercept	4	9.4522	1.7154	0.1834
arcsine duty factor	Common model	2	9.7178		
	Variable Slopes	3	9.6154	1.6069	0.2069
	Variable Intercept	3	9.4848	3.7081	0.056
	Variable Slope + Intercept	4	9.3603	2.864	0.0602

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